

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20734269>

THE IMPACT OF CROSS-CULTURE ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN CENTRAL ASIA

Khamdamova Sitora Safarovna

Senior Lecturer, Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs,
Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor

Abstract: *This article examines the impact of cross-cultural interactions on the development of science in Central Asia. Particular attention is given to the Samanid period, during which scholars produced significant works in both Persian and Arabic, contributing to a rich intellectual and cultural heritage. The study highlights the role of Iranian-origin statesmen in promoting the Persian language and literature, including the patronage of Rudaki Samarqandi and the translation of important religious and historical texts into Persian. Furthermore, the article explores how the long-term interaction between Persian and Turkic cultural traditions fostered a dynamic environment for scientific, literary, and cultural advancement in Central Asia. The findings demonstrate that scientific progress is closely linked to cultural exchange, mutual influence, and intellectual cooperation among diverse communities.*

Keywords: *Central Asia, cross-cultural interaction, scientific development, Samanid dynasty, Persian language, Arabic language, Rudaki Samarqandi, al-Bal'ami, translation movement, intellectual heritage, Persian-Turkic cultural synthesis, cultural integration, intercultural dialogue, literature, history.*

Introduction. During this era, scholars and thinkers capable of creating bilingual works in both Persian and Arabic worked extensively on this creative heritage, leaving behind a legacy of invaluable literature.

Furthermore, during the Samanid period, ministers of Iranian descent exerted a profound influence on the development of the Persian language. For instance, the greatest patron of Rudaki Samarqandi (d. 941 CE), who is widely recognized as the founder of New Persian, was Abu'l-Fazl al-Bal'ami (d. 940 CE), a minister of Iranian origin from that era. Similarly, during the tenure of the aforementioned minister's son, Abu Ali al-Bal'ami (who served as vizier and passed away between 992 and 997 CE), the Holy Quran was translated into the Persian language alongside the Persian

translation of the History of al-Tabari. [Aydin Usta. The First Muslim Turkic State. Bio-factor Press. Tashkent, 2025. p. 55.]

This process demonstrates that cultures develop not in isolation, but through continuous dialogue and mutual influence: elements of language, religion, art, customs, or science from one culture blend into another, giving rise to new hybrid forms. For example, the centuries-long blending of Iranian Persian culture with Turkic elements in Central Asia shaped the cultures of the Uzbek, Tajik, and other peoples; here, the intertwining footprints of both cultures in poetry, architecture, music, and cuisine are entirely inseparable.

The unique charm and expressive power of language, alongside scientific achievements, serve as a fundamental factor in the creation of a unique literary and cultural heritage.

Literature review. During the Samanid period, although figures who composed in Persian and wrote major works in their respective fields emerged—such as Daqiqi, Rudaki, Kisa'i, and Ferdowsi—they simultaneously supported writers and poets who created works in Arabic without any discrimination. In fact, this practice was a matter of prestige and honor for medieval rulers. State authorities protected and supported such individuals to strengthen their state and, particularly, reinforce their own rule. Essentially, the Persian language experienced its "golden age" during the Ghaznavid, Seljuk, Anatolian Seljuk, and Khwarazmshah periods. Unlike the Samanids, these aforementioned states even used Persian in official state affairs. Furthermore, a sharp linguistic division later occurred within the Islamic world. While Persian exerted a massive influence in the East, Arabic maintained its dominance in the West. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Tashkent, 2025. P. 52.]

The unique charm and expressive power of language, alongside scientific achievements, serve as a fundamental factor in the creation of a unique literary and cultural heritage.

Sogdian inscriptions found on coins dating back to the pre-Islamic Hephthalite (White Hun) and Turkic Khaganate periods serve as an example of their continued use of the existing language to facilitate administration. Administratively, the Samanids followed directly in the footsteps of the Abbasids. Consequently, they also utilized Arabic in official state affairs. Notable works written in Arabic during this period include: *Mafatih al-Ulum* by Abu Abdullah Muhammad al-Khwarazmi (d. 997), poems by al-Iskafi, the head of the chancery (*diwan al-rasail*) during the reigns of Nuh I (943–956) and Abd al-Malik I (956–963), *Tarikh-i Bukhara* (History of Bukhara) by Narshakhi, *Tarikh al-Yamini* by Utbi, and *Kitab Akhbar Wulat Khurasan* by Salami. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Tashkent, 2025. pp. 53-55.]

Another remarkable aspect of the city of Balkh is that it served as one of the most vital Buddhist centers during the Western Turkic Khaganate period. For instance, due to its abundance of Buddhist statues, the city was also referred to as “Little Rajagriha.” Balkh was home to 100 monasteries and approximately 3,000 Buddhist monks belonging to the Hinayana (Lesser Vehicle) school, with the renowned Navbahor temple serving as the central sanctuary for Buddhists. On a copper fals minted between 887 and 893 CE by the Samanid Emir Nuh ibn Asad, and on a dirham minted in Fergana in 969 CE on behalf of Mansur ibn Nuh, one can find two interlocking squares (a mandala)-a symbol tied to Buddhist cosmology-inscribed within a circle. [Aydin Usta. *The First Muslim Turkic State*. Bio-factor Press. Tashkent, 2025. pp. 63-64.]

Even today, these cities are not just historical monuments but living spiritual centers that attract millions of pilgrims and tourists. Serving as symbols of religious tolerance, spiritual purity, and human values, they contribute to strengthening peace and harmony among nations.

Thus, while Central Asian cities are centers of cultural heritage, they have also preserved their unique place as sacred sanctuaries of religious faith and spiritual-cultural values. This heritage is an integral part of humanity’s shared cultural and spiritual wealth.

Furthermore, the Samanids adopted the administrative structure of the Islamic state under Abbasid rule as a model for themselves. In addition, they always maintained good relations with neighboring factions. Although they fully exercised their ruling rights, they contented themselves with the title of amir (governor) out of respect for the Abbasids. According to sources, the Samanid army utilized the traditional "Turkic combat" method in battles. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. P. 76.]

Discussion. Religious and cultural values-such as compassion, justice, spiritual purity, and respect for family and society-deeply permeated the core layers of culture, influencing the moral norms, festivals, music, and literature of the people. Rather than isolating cultures, this process demonstrated development through mutual enrichment, shaping a shared system of values among nations.

These cities served as religious educational, cultural, and spiritual centers, with Bukhara and Samarkand rising to prominence in the Middle Ages as the most influential scientific and spiritual hubs of the Islamic world. The madrasas established there, such as the Ulugbek Madrasa and the Miri Arab Madrasa, taught not only religious but also secular sciences, serving as spiritual destinations for millions of pilgrims.

Religious faith and values became an inseparable part of culture in these cities. Sufi teachings, such as the Naqshbandiya and Yasaviya orders, shaped the moral norms of the people, including values like hospitality, tolerance, and mutual respect. These values were reflected in the architecture, art, and daily life of the cities, enriching their cultural heritage with spiritual meaning.

Today's globalized world, religions continue to serve as vital instruments of cultural dialogue, fostering mutual understanding and respect among people of different faiths. The culture diffused through religious beliefs and values is not merely a heritage of the past, but a driving force that guarantees peace, tolerance, and cultural-spiritual unity in modern societies.

Furthermore, it should not be overlooked that while the Sassanids adhered to the Zoroastrian faith, the Turkic Khaganate, which ruled Western Turkestan, embraced Buddhism in addition to its primary belief in Tengrism (Kök-Tengri). [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. pp. 89-90.] This process of assimilation enriches cultures, enhances diversity, dismantles stereotypes, and strengthens mutual understanding between nations. History demonstrates that the most successful and enduring cultures emerged precisely from such syntheses, harmonizing the strengths of one culture with the richness of another.

On the other hand, the Samanid dynasty modeled the linguistic and administrative organization of its established structure after the Abbasids and the Arabic language. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. p. 94.] The Samanid period was not only an era of political independence and economic prosperity in the history of Central Asia, but also a crucial milestone that facilitated the deep dissemination of Islamic religious values and beliefs, as well as the delineation of core Islamic doctrines.

During this period, under Samanid rule, the Sunni branch of Islam—specifically Hanafi jurisprudence (fiqh)—became firmly established both officially and among the public within the region. Rulers such as Ismail Samani, Ahmad ibn Ismail, and others built mosques, madrasas, and scientific centers, thereby encouraging religious education. Bukhara earned the moniker “Sharif” (Noble), becoming one of the most influential spiritual, cultural, and scientific centers of the Islamic world.

Religious and moral values such as justice, the pursuit of knowledge, tolerance, and hospitality occupied a leading position in state policy and social life. By supporting the Hanafi school of thought, the Samanids prevented religious conflicts in the region, which in turn ensured peace and stability.

Core Islamic disciplines, including Quranic and Hadith sciences, jurisprudence (fiqh), and Sufism, were clearly delineated during this era. For instance, the works of

great scholars like Imam Bukhari and Imam Tirmidhi were compiled and promoted, while thinkers such as Al-Farabi and Ibn Sina advanced Islamic philosophy. These teachings became the bedrock of not only religious life, but also of scientific, cultural, and spiritual endeavors.

Religious beliefs and values spread during the Samanid period deeply penetrated the mentality of Central Asian peoples, still forming the basis of today's values such as tolerance, respect for science, and spiritual purity. This period demonstrates that Islam was established in the region through peaceful and enlightened ways, laying the foundation for spiritual unity and solidarity among nations.

The Samanid period, with the spread of religious values and the precise formation of Islamic teachings, remained a crucial stage defining the cultural and spiritual identity of Central Asia not only for its own time but also for subsequent centuries. This heritage continues to exist in the cultural and spiritual life of peoples today, promoting the principles of peace and enlightenment.

As highlighted above, the creedal (Maturidiyya) and doctrinal (Sawad al-A'zam) boundaries and directions of Hanafism were defined during the Samanid period. [Aydin Usta. The First Muslim Turkic State. Bio-factor press. Tashkent, 2025. p. 95.]

Looking back at the historical development of Central Asia, great scientists and thinkers who created works in the Arabic and Persian languages left a massive and incomparable mark on cultural heritage through their active efforts during the Samanid period.

During this era, cities like Bukhara and Samarkand turned into global scientific and cultural centers; works written in Arabic and Persian on philosophy, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, philology, and literature enriched human civilization not only in their own time but also in subsequent centuries.

For instance, while Abu Nasr al-Farabi commented on Aristotle's ideas in philosophy and logic, strengthening the foundation of Islamic philosophy, Ibn Sina revolutionized medicine and philosophy on a global scale with his book "The Canon of Medicine," and Abu Rayhan al-Biruni demonstrated an example of scientific accuracy and open-mindedness through his research in geography, astronomy, and history.

We would not be mistaken to say that these scientists' creation of works in Arabic and Persian showcased the highest level of bilingualism; the Arabic language was used as a scientific tool, while the Persian language served as a medium for literary and spiritual expression. Their efforts-including scientific travels, debates, writing books, and teaching-intensified cultural exchange and led to a deep synthesis of Persian and Arabic cultures.

The cultural heritage and poetry created by the Samanid period formed the basis of Central Asian peoples' identity and directly influenced world culture as well.

The efforts and legacy of the scholars who worked during the Samanid period served as a spiritual and intellectual bridge between different peoples.

As a result of these appointments, the Samanids became one of the primary factors influencing events in the Eastern Islamic world. In this regard, while maintaining good relations with the Abbasids and the Tahirids, who ruled Khurasan on their behalf, they further consolidated and increased their power in Transoxiana. They supported the military activities of these two political forces. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. pp. 100-101.]

Thus, due to this victory, the Samanids became the most powerful state in the Eastern Islamic world. The success they achieved in this manner provided them with the opportunity to seize dominance over the territory of Khurasan as well. Beyond its mineral and agricultural wealth, Khurasan was situated at the crossroads of major trade routes. The unification of Khurasan and Transoxiana under a single, centralized administration granted the Samanids vast economic power in addition to extensive territories. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. p. 110.]

Turkic military campaign tactics significantly contributed to expanding the lands of the Samanid dynasty and strengthening their political power in the region.

Furthermore, during this military campaign, the city of Rayy-which held immense commercial importance and was situated at the crossroads of three major trade routes of that era (the Great Silk Road, the Spice Route, and the Fur Route)-was also conquered by the Samanids. These recent successes provided the Samanids not only with political leverage but also with the opportunity to bring regional trade under their direct control. [Aydin Usta. *Ilk musulmon turk davlati*. Bio-factor press. Toshkent, 2025. p. 112.]

Among the intellectuals who remained in Central Asia, Shamsiddin Shohid in his epic poem *Layli and Majnun*, and Junaydullah Hozhi in his epic poem *Yusuf and Zulaikha*, mentioned the names of Greek philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, and Pythagoras; however, their philosophical heritage failed to provide the necessary insights and reflections required for science.

Intellectuals like Turdi, Makhmur, and Hakimkhan Tura, who lived in the Kokand Khanate, alongside Khoziq and Ahmad Donish, who lived in the Emirate of Bukhara, realized that science, culture, and spiritual life in the Central Asian states had fallen into decay, and that serious changes were urgently needed in the life of society.

The transmission process of culture: culture can be passed down from generation to generation. Parents transmit cultural traits to their children, who, in turn, pass them on to their own children, and so forth.

According to archaeological and historical sources, for several millennia, the teachings of Zoroastrianism through the Avesta and the teachings of Islam through the Quran brought Arab, Iranian, and Turanian peoples, as well as Persian and Turkic nations, closer together in the spheres of culture and spirituality. [Maytdinova G. Dialog tsivilizatsiy v Sredneaziatskom areale Velikogo Shelkovogo puti. Istoricheskiy opyt integratsii. – Dushanbe "Donish", 2015. - p. 5.] The Avesta reflects that Zoroastrians were in a state of war with the Turkic peoples, and Kay Khosrow was at war with Afrasiab, a situation that is also confirmed by historical sources. On the other hand, sources mention that during the conquest of Alexander the Great and his war with Darius, the Turkic peoples of Central Asia acted as allies to the Iranians. Xenophon, a participant in the events, confirms this in his work *Cyropaedia*. Alisher Navoi also writes about the Khwarazmians as allies to the Iranians in his epic poem *Saddi Iskandari* (The Wall of Alexander).

Yusuf Balasaguni expresses his cultural and educational ideas in an artistic, poetic language. Instead of the word “enlightenment” (ma’rifat), he uses the Turkic word “bilig”(knowledge). The Karakhanid thinker highlights that during his lifetime, the Turkic peoples failed to build a unified, centralized, powerful state. Instead, various Turkic tribes and clans engaged in internal conflicts and devastating wars for centuries, falling significantly behind the Arabs and Persians in artistic literature and spiritual culture.

In the 10th-11th centuries, the Iranian and Persian peoples possessed great poets and scholars such as Daqiqi, Rudaki, Shahid Balkhi, Ferdowsi, Abu Bakr al-Razi, Nasir Khusraw, Farrukhi, Asadi Tusi, Anvari, Sanai, and others. The great scholars of Central Asian Turkic peoples, such as Muhammad al-Farabi, al-Biruni, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abu Bakr al-Khwarizmi, Abu Abdullah al-Khwarizmi, and Ibn Sina created their works in Arabic, while Afzaluddin Khaqani and Nizami Ganjavi wrote in Persian.

Til arslon turur, kor, eshikda yotur,
Ayo evluk, arsig, ishingni etur.

Meaning: Look, the tongue is a lion that lies at the doorstep; oh homeowner, beware, control it, or it will take your head.

That is, understand and see that your tongue is like a lion guarding the door of your house from enemies; be a true man and settle your affairs wisely using good language.

All thinkers, particularly Eastern thinkers, pay great attention to language, which distinguishes humans from the animal kingdom, and to the word, which is the mirror of the human spiritual world.

This tongue is the interpreter for learning and wisdom,

Know that the tongue guides a person and illuminates their path.

[Yusuf Hos Hajib. Qutadgu Bilig. / Uzbek Literature. Anthology. Volume 1. – Tashkent: Ozdavadabiynashr, 1959. – P. 38.]

That is, a person reads and gains knowledge through the tongue as an interpreter; the tongue guides a man and illuminates his path. Unlike his contemporary Mahmud al-Kashgari, Yusuf Balasaguni approaches language issues from a more philosophical perspective. In his view, language is a spiritual phenomenon closely linked to human intellect, reason, and worldview.

A word spoken with knowledge is counted as wisdom,

An ignorant person's word costs them their own head.

[Yusuf Hos Hajib. Qutadgu Bilig. / Uzbek Literature. Anthology. Volume 1. – Tashkent: Ozdavadabiynashr, 1959. – P. 37.]

That is, one who speaks with knowledge is considered a scholar, while an ignorant person who speaks without knowing will lose their head. Many conflicts in life arise from speaking without knowing, without thinking, or in anger. According to the thinker, loquacity and talkativeness are also harmful qualities:

I saw no benefit at all in speaking too much,

Nor did I gain any favor by repeatedly speaking.

[Yusuf Khas Hajib. Qutadgu Bilig. / Uzbek Literature. Anthology. Volume 1. – Tashkent: Ozdavadabiynashr, 1959. – P. 39.]

That is, I saw no benefit in excessive talking, nor did repeating words bring me closer to the ruler.

That is, a brave man lives on without aging through two virtues: one is his good, noble deed/action, and the other is his good word, through which he lives **on in** the memory of many generations.

Conclusion. Yusuf Balasaguni's educational ideas drew inspiration from the enlightened and philosophical views of the great humanist thinkers who lived shortly before his time and during his era. The scholars and poets of that period who lived in Mavarannahr and Khorasan and wrote in the Persian language paid great attention in their works to the issue of humanity (odamiylik), which is the source of humanist ideas. By humanity and humaneness, these thinkers meant acquiring education and upbringing, striving for high goals, being free and spiritually healthy, living in peace and harmony using intellect and reason, without conflict between society and the

individual. Almighty God also commands people to live in this manner. People should learn from life through intellect and wisdom. As the 10th-century poet Abu Abdullah Rudaki stated:

Four things were given to me for the wise to ponder:

Good health, a good character, a good name, and a good thought. [Rudaki. Lyrics. – Dushanbe “Irfon” 1976. – P. 119.]

If a person possesses true humanity, even the oppression of cruel officials cannot defeat them. Humaneness is the greatest wealth.

Yusuf Hos Hajib also views humanity through the lens of good character, communication culture, morals and manners, and kind speech:

If you desire safety, count this your speech,

Do not let unseemly words come from your tongue.

[Yusuf Khass Hajib. Kutadgu Bilig. / Uzbek Literature. Collection. Volume 1. – T.: Ozdavadabiynashr, 1959. – P. 37.]

References:

1. Aydin Usta. The First Muslim Turkic State. Bio-Factor Press. Tashkent, 2025.
2. Mutribi. Tazkirat ush-Shuara (Biography of Poets). – T.: 2006.
3. Maytdinova G. Dialogue of Civilizations in the Central Asian Area of the Great Silk Road: Historical Experience of Integration. – Dushanbe "Donish", 2015.
4. Kurbanmamadov A. China in the Works of Alisher Navoi. "Uzbekistan - China: Development of Historical, Cultural, Scientific, and Economic Relations." // International Scientific and Practical Conference, November 15, 2017. – T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.
5. Kroeber A.L. Configurations of Culture Growth. – Berkeley: University of California Press, 1944.
6. Yusuf Khass Hajib. Kutadgu Bilig (The Wisdom of Royal Glory). / Uzbek Literature. Collection. Volume 1. – T.: Ozdavadabiynashr, 1959.
7. Rudaki. Lyrics. – Dushanbe “Irfon”, 1976.